

Short communication

***Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) has reached the Italian island of Pianosa**

TORSTEN VAN DER HEYDEN^{1*}, MORENA NAVA²

¹ Immenweide 83, D-22523 Hamburg, Germany; e-mail: tmvdh@web.de; ² Department of Biotechnology and Biosciences, University of Milano-Bicocca, Piazza della Scienza 2, I-20126 Milan, Italy; e-mail: m.nava36@campus.unimib.it

Abstract. The first record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) for the Italian island of Pianosa is reported. Additional information on the finding is given.

Key words: Heteroptera, *Zelus renardii*, distribution, new record, invasive species, Pianosa, Italy, Mediterranean Region.

The invasive Nearctic assassin bug *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) has colonised various European countries, where it is mainly distributed in the Mediterranean Region. Recently, Kment & van der Heyden (2022) published a list of the known distribution of the species on the European continent and adjacent islands.

So far, in Italy the species has been reported from the mainland (Apulia, Campania, Lazio, Liguria) and from the islands of Sardinia and Sicily (Kment & van der Heyden 2022).

Herein, we report *Z. renardii* from the Italian island of Pianosa.

Material examined: ITALY: Pianosa, Lat.: 42.600537, Long.: 10.087879, 11.IX.2022, 1 ex., leg. M. Nava.

Pianosa is a small island of about 10 km², located in the Tuscan Archipelago in the Tyrrhenian Sea, 26 km west of the Italian mainland.

On 11.IX.2022, the second author captured an adult female of *Z. renardii* on Pianosa (Fig. 1). The specimen was found on *Juniperus* cf. *phoenicea* L. (Cupressaceae) ten meters away from the sea and was captured by using an entomological net. When captured, it had a voluminous abdomen. Shortly after being found, on 12.IX.2022, the specimen laid eggs in captivity (Fig. 2).

Acknowledgements

The second author would like to thank the following organisations for the opportunity to participate in the Summer School in Entomology “Meet the Experts!” on the islands of Elba and Pianosa and to sample some specimens: World Biodiversity Association, Nuovo Gruppo Entomologico Toscano, Successione Ecologica APS in collaboration with NatLab and Parco Nazionale Arcipelago Toscano.

Fig. 1. Female of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 captured on Pianosa, Italy; after oviposition (photo: Morena Nava).

Fig. 2. Cluster of eggs laid by the female of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 captured on Pianosa, Italy (photo: Morena Nava).

References

Kment P., van der Heyden T. 2022. *Zelus renardii* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae): first records from Croatia, Montenegro, and an accidental introduction to the Czech Republic. *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica* **16**: 7–14.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6373854>

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Received: 13 September 2022
Accepted: 18 November 2022